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Conference Paper · August 2025

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Chef Nata: A Gamified AI Assistant to Reduce Household Food Waste through Micro-Interactions and 8-Bit Aesthetics

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Abstract: This paper presents the concept, theoretical foundation, and initial prototype of a mobile application aimed at reducing household food waste through interaction with a virtual AI assistant called "Chef Nata." Inspired by 8-bit game aesthetics and micro-interactions, the app seeks to engage users playfully and effectively, offering personalized recommendations supported by large language models. This is a conceptual and design-focused study grounded in principles of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and digital sustainability, proposing future directions for empirical validation.

Palavras-chave: food waste; human-computer interaction; artificial intelligence; micro-interactions; playful design; sustainability

INTRODUCTION

Food waste is one of the most pressing issues of our time, affecting food security, the environment, and the economy. This work proposes a digital approach to mitigate this problem through a mobile application centered on a gamified virtual assistant named "Chef Nata." The solution combines generative AI, micro-interactions, and retro 8-bit game aesthetics to increase user engagement and promote sustainable behavior change.

Recent literature highlights that intelligent information systems can significantly contribute to promoting sustainability, especially when designed with awareness of human-centered values and behaviors (Santos et al., 2025). These systems, when thoughtfully integrated into daily practices, can shift user habits toward more responsible consumption.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Recent studies show that digital applications can reduce food waste through recommendations, gamification, and data visualization (Ahmadzadeh et al., 2023; Castro et al., 2023; Mastorakis et al., 2024). AI-driven interventions enable personalization (Nohria et al., 2023), while the use of engaging aesthetics can amplify the impact of the message, as discussed in the "aesthetic turn" in HCI (Udsen & Jørgensen, 2005). Chef Nata synthesizes these approaches by providing a playful and personalized interface, with a gender-neutral character aligned with recent trends in inclusive interaction design.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The app's development followed an iterative process focusing on:

- Defining functional requirements;
- Designing the persona and narrative (Chef Nata);
- Prototyping the interface and micro-interactions;
- Integrating AI (LLMs) for personalized recommendations;
- Internal testing for usability and interaction flow coherence.

No external user validation was conducted at this stage. The focus is on presenting the system rationale, design decisions, and future possibilities.

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Chef Nata is a responsive 8-bit avatar that interacts with users through micro-interactions. The interface includes:

- An introductory narrative screen;
- A camera interface for scanning food items.
- AI-driven generation of personalized advice on recipes, storage, and reuse.

Figure 1: Basic structure of the app flow.

Figure 2: Screenshots of the "Chef Nata" app. Left: Introduction screen with 8-bit avatar. Middle: Camera interface for scanning food items. Right: AI-driven food waste reduction advice.

The recommendations use a natural language model to adapt content to the user's food context, focusing on engagement and practicality.

DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The proposal demonstrates potential for behavioral intervention through engaging design and emerging technologies. Limitations include the absence of empirical studies, potential AI bias, and adoption challenges. Future work should include:

- User testing to measure engagement and impact;
- Longitudinal evaluation of behavioral change;
- Feature expansion and cultural localization.

CONCLUSION

Chef Nata proposes an innovative, accessible, and inclusive solution to reduce food waste. By combining AI, game aesthetics, and micro-interactions, it contributes to the discourse on sustainability and digital technologies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project was developed as part of the coursework for the class on Human-Computer Interaction, by Professor Inês Martins Sequeira Rodolfo. The author acknowledges her valuable contributions and the mentorship she has provided.

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